

CONSIDERATIONS ON INDEPENDENT WORDS AND NOUNS

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Abstract: This article discusses independent word groups characteristic of the Uzbek language. It also discusses different views on independent word groups and analyzes these views through several points of view. At the end of the article, a conclusion is made, giving personal views on the elimination of these differences.

Key words: morphology, vocabulary, noun, adjective, verb, number, pronoun, adverb.

Morphology (Greek: morphe - "form" and ... logia - "teaching") (in linguistics it means the teaching of form) - 1) morphological construction of language; 2) the doctrine of word forms. In the first sense, it means an object, and in the second sense, it means the branch of linguistics that studies this object. It is also divided into 3 large groups: 1) independent word groups; 2) auxiliary words; 3) intermediate words (separate words)

Morphology. learns word groups, their specific grammatical meanings, grammatical categories specific to each group, the grammatical form and grammatical meanings that create these categories, and the city. Just as a language is a system, its independent word groups also form a unique system. In turn, the morphological system consists of specific sub-systems. By elucidating the essence of each of them, the independent word groups of the language are studied as a whole, as a system. In the textbooks of general secondary schools, nouns are divided into common nouns and common nouns according to their meaning.

The following types of proper nouns are presented in the textbook: 1) place names; 2) personal names; 3) names of organizations, enterprises, institutions; 4) names of water bodies; 5) names of historical dates and holidays. Relative nouns are also classified into 4 groups: 1) personal nouns; 2) object nouns; 3) nouns of place; 4) activity-process nouns.

Nouns are divided into 4 types according to their structure: 1) simple; 2) joint; 3) couple; 4) repeated.

The textbook for students of academic lyceums does not provide theoretical information about the types of nouns according to their semantic relationship and types according to their structure.

U. Tursunov divides nouns into the following lexical-grammatical types:

- 1) proper nouns and related nouns;
- 2) concrete and abstract nouns;
- 3) singular and collective nouns.

Famous horses are divided into the following types:

- 1) names, surnames, nicknames and nicknames of people;
- 2) geographical, administrative-territorial names, historical events, literary and scientific works, names of institutions and enterprises;
- 3) atronomic names;

4) special terms for animals. Sh. Rahmatullaev the largest classification of noun lexemes is based on who and what questions (noun lexemes that are the answer to the question who noun lexemes object nouns); in the Eastern world, including the Uzbeks, the division of existence into two: person and person; underlining that the concept of nokishi includes animate objects as well as inanimate objects, he says that, accordingly, the classification of noun lexemes in Uzbek according to the meaning of person and nokishi differs from the classification of animate and inanimate in Russian. The scientist, in turn, divides common nouns into several types of meaning:

1) nouns that do not have a lexical meaning and are used as conditional marks:

a) a person's name, patronymic, surname, nickname (Abror Hidoyatov - originally had a lexical meaning, but after becoming a proper noun, the lexical meaning disappeared; accordingly, such proper nouns are conditionally included among lexemes) ;

b) names for pets;

d) geographical names whose meaning cannot be explained at the moment (such as Hadra, Kuva. The parts of place names such as Mirzachol, Yangiyer have not lost their lexical meaning,

so the lexical meaning is understood from such a geographical name) ;

e) names of persons or things conditionally attached to the organization, institution.

2) The lexical meaning remains valid in the following types of nouns:

a) in the names of state organizations, offices and institutions; these are usually equal to the stable combination: Republic of Uzbekistan;

b) names of newspapers, magazines, books: "Enlightenment", "World Literature".

Cognate nouns, in turn, are divided into the following types of meaning:

1. Participial nouns and plural nouns: boy, girl; boyfriend and girlfriend

Collective meaning of objects is a characteristic of even nouns, and in this respect it is opposed to odd nouns.

2. Physical (concrete) and mental (abstract) nouns.

3. Single nouns and singular nouns: swallow, sideboard; eye, boot. Nouns, in turn, are divided into the following meaning types:

1) nouns denoting a single-dual object: kolok, kol (an important sign means a double object);

2) nouns denoting singular-plural objects: hair, eyelashes (an important sign is plural objects);

3) nouns that mean the object as a group: forest, crowd (always mean several objects as a whole group).

4. Nouns of countable objects and nouns of uncountable objects. Countable objects make up the main part of related nouns. The nouns denoting uncountable substances are mainly the names of substances: sand, ice, smoke.

R. Saifullaeva classifies nouns according to their different characteristics. First of all, nouns are divided into types such as nouns and nouns according to whether they denote the name of one of the objects of the same type or the common name of objects of this type. The famous horse, in turn, is divided into the following types:

- 1) name, surname, nickname of people;
- 2) geographical name;
- 3) name of organization, institution, enterprise;
- 4) name of heavenly luminaries;
- 5) the name of the historical event;
- 6) the name of the animal;
- 7) product name;

8) a name representing a divine concept. A relative noun is divided into specific and abstract nouns according to the nature of the concept it expresses. A specific type is grouped as follows:

- 1) substance name;
- 2) the name of the description of the person;
- 3) product name;
- 4) plant name;
- 5) name of the place;
- 6) the name of the amount;
- 7) name of the organization-institution;
- 8) time, the name of the moment.

R. Sayfullaeva divides nouns into simple and complex ones, and complex nouns into double, repeated and compound nouns.

R. Sayfullaeva emphasizes that nouns are made in two ways - affixation and composition. Accordingly, there is an affixal and composite form of noun formation. This pattern is also productive and unproductive in its place; It is divided into productive and non-productive types. Compound and double nouns are formed by the method of composition.

In particular, U. Tursunov structurally divides non-categorical noun forms into 3

types:1) synthetic form; 2) analytical form; 3) double and repeated form.

Accordingly, the synthetic forms of the noun are divided into the following types according to their meaning: 1) diminutive forms: -cha, -chak, -chak, -chik; 2) caress form: -jan, -khan, -oy, -niso, -gina, -kina, -qina, -(a) loq; 3) dependent form: -niki; 4) the form of place sign: in -; 5) limit form: -gacha (-kacha, -kacha).

The analytical form is created with the help of an assistant. The double form is formed by combining two nouns and means generalization, summation, strengthening.

In conclusion, it can be noted that in Uzbek linguistics, there are different views on the word group of nouns.

List of used literature:

1. Mahmudov N v.b. 7th grade Mother tongue textbook. T.: Spirituality, 2013.
2. Nurmonov A. 6th grade Mother tongue textbook. T.: Image, 2013
3. Nurmonov A. etc. Modern Uzbek literary language. Academic Lyceum. Textbook for 2nd year students. T.: Ilm-Ziya, 2010.
4. Current issues of Uzbek linguistics. (Proceedings of the scientific theoretical conference of the Republic. T; 2013. No. 7.
5. Rahmatullayev Sh. Modern literary Uzbek language. T., 2006.
6. Sayfullayeva R. Modern Uzbek literary language. T., 2009.